

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF EMULGEL CONTAINING KOJIC ACID DIPALMITATE AND NIACINAMIDE FOR ANTI-ACNE, ANTI-AGEING, SKIN BRIGHTENING AND HYPERPIGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Emulgel are the combination of emulsion and gels. Main aim of emulgel drug delivery is delivery of hydrophobic drugs so that hydrophobic drugs can also enjoy various advantages of gel formulation. This study describes the formulation and assessment of an emulgel, a combination of a topical drug delivery system, using Kojic acid Dipalmitate and Niacinamide for the treatment of hyperpigmentation and skin disorders. Direct targeting skin disorders without first-pass effects and gastrointestinal complications. Selective targeting of drugs increases efficacy, particularly for drugs with shorter biological half-lives. The emulgel facilitates the delivery of hydrophobic drugs through controlled release systems, increasing drug penetration and reducing irritation. The emulgel formulation involves the combination of an oil phase (Kojic acid Dipalmitate) with a gel matrix using gelling agents such as Carbopol 934. The formulation demonstrated stable pH (5.5-6.5), suitable viscosity (ranging from 732-856 cps), and good

spreadability, ensuring its suitability for topical applications. Among the formulations, F1 was recognized for its best organoleptic characteristics, drug content and release studies

suggesting commercial feasibility. In vivo studies and comparative analysis with existing formulations are recommended to determine clinical efficacy and safety. Evaluation of current advanced delivery systems and formulation improvements is recommended for improved therapeutic results. The study clearly indicates that the emulgel formulation developed has potential as a stable and effective topical formulation.

KEYWORDS: Kojic Acid Dipalmitate, Niacinamide, Emulgel, Hyperpigmentation, skin brightening, topical preparation.

INTRODUCTION

Skin hyperpigmentation is a widespread dermatological condition that is defined by the excessive production of melanin, leading to dark patches on the skin. Skin hyperpigmentation includes conditions like melasma, freckles, and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. These conditions have a significant impact on the physical appearance and psychological confidence of affected individuals.^[1]

Kojic acid Dipalmitate is a stable ester derivative of kojic acid, which is synthesized by esterification with palmitic acid. Kojic acid Dipalmitate has potent tyrosinase inhibition and melanin production inhibition.^[2]

Niacinamide, also known as vitamin B3, is a versatile ingredient that is widely used in dermatology. It works by decreasing hyperpigmentation through the inhibition of melanosome transfer from melanocytes to keratinocytes. In addition, it also improves skin barrier function, has anti-inflammatory properties, and hydrates the skin. Emulgel is a new topical drug delivery system that is created by the incorporation of an emulsion into a gel base. Emulgel has the benefits of both emulsions and gels, including improved stability, increased spreadability, non-greasy texture, and improved patient compliance. Emulgel are particularly useful for hydrophobic drugs.^[3]

The current research work is centered on the formulation and evaluation of a topical emulgel formulation of Kojic acid Dipalmitate and Niacinamide for the treatment of hyperpigmentation and skin disorders. The current research work opens avenues to investigate the emulgel formulation as an innovative drug delivery system that has the potential to entrap both lipophilic (Kojic acid Dipalmitate) and hydrophilic (Niacinamide) drugs in a single formulation, thus enhancing the availability of the drug at the target site.

The research work encompasses the Preformulation studies and compatibility studies of the drugs with excipients. Optimization of the formulation variables such as the type and concentration of gelling agents, emulsifiers, and penetration enhancers. Evaluation of the physicochemical properties such as pH, viscosity, Spreadability, homogeneity, drug content, and in-vitro drug release profile. Stability studies under appropriate storage conditions to determine the shelf life of the formulation. The current research work also has implications in laying down a basis for In-vivo studies and dermatological safety studies in future research work. Comparative studies with conventional creams and gels to prove the efficacy of the formulation. Scale-up, quality control, and industrial applications of the formulation in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industry for topical products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A) MATERIALS

The formulation of these emulgel was done by the ingredients of Kojic acid Dipalmitate, Niacinamide, Carbopol 934, liquid paraffin, span 20, tween 20, glycerin, sodium metabisulphite, triethanolamine, lavender oil was purchased from Viva Scientific Company.

B) METHODS^[4]

STEP1: Formulation of Emulsion O/W.

STEP2: Formulation of gel base.

STEP3: Incorporation of emulsion into gel base with continuous stirring.

FORMULATION OF KOJIC ACID AND NIACINAMIDE EMULGEL^[4]

The gel base of the formulations was prepared by mixing Carbopol 934 with purified water using a mechanical shaker with constant stirring at a moderate speed, and then tri ethanol amine (TEA) was added drop by drop to the gel base to create the desired consistency as well as adjust the pH to 6-6.5. The oil phase of the emulsion was prepared by dissolving span 20 in light liquid paraffin, and the aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving tween 20 in glycerin and purified water. Kojic acid Dipalmitate was dissolved in ethanol, and niacinamide was dissolved in purified water. Both the oily and aqueous phases were separately heated to 70-80⁰ C, and then the oily phase was added to the aqueous phase with constant stirring until cooled to room temperature. The drug solutions were added to the emulsion and then mixed with the gel in 1:1 ratio with gentle stirring to form the emulgel. Four different formulations denoted as F1,F2,F3 and F4 were prepared as per the formulation chart described in the Table No.1. The formulated emulgel was presented in Figure. No 1.

Figure No. 1: Formulated Kojic Acid Dipalmitate And Niacinamide Emulgel.

Table No. 1: Formulation Chart of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate and Niacinamide emulgel.

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODE			
		F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Kojic acid Dipalmitate	2 g	2 g	2 g	2 g
2	Niacinamide	4 g	4 g	4 g	4 g
3	Carbopol 934	1 g	1 g	1 g	1 g
4	Liquid paraffin	5 ml	7.5 ml	5 ml	7.5 ml
5	Span 20	1.5 ml	0.9 ml	0.9 ml	1.5 ml
6	Tween 20	1 ml	0.6 ml	0.6 ml	1 ml
7	Glycerin	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml
8	Lavender oil	0.3 ml	0.3 ml	0.3 ml	0.3 ml
9	Sodium metabisulphite	0.01 g	0.005 g	0.005 g	0.01 g
10	Triethanolamine	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml
11	Distilled Water q.s to	100 ml	100 ml	100 ml	100 ml

EVALUATION OF EMULGEL^[5,6,7]

The formulated products were evaluated for different parameters to arrive at the ideal formulation. The parameters are physical examination, pH, Viscosity, Spreadability and drug content were performed.

1. Physical Examination^[8]

State: The state was observed by visual appearance.

Colour: The Colour of the formulation was compared with white and black background. The results were recorded.

Odour: The Odour of emulgel was compared by mixing it with water and smelling. The results were recorded.

2. pH^[9]

A 1% solution of emulgel was prepared and used to measure pH by digital pH meter. The results were observed.

3. Viscosity^[10]

The rheological property of emulgel sample was measured by Brookfield viscometer and the readings were recorded.

4. Spreadability^[11,12]

A lower glass slide was fixed on this block. An excess of the prepared emulgel (about 1gm) under study was placed on this ground slide. The emulgel formulation was then sandwiched between this slide and another glass slide having the dimension of fixed ground slide and provided with a hook. A weight of 100 g was placed on the top of the two slides for 5 min to expel air and to provide a uniform film of the gel between the slides. Excess of the emulgel was scrapped off from the edges. The upper slide was then subjected to a pull of 20 g weight with the help of a string attached to the hook and the time (in seconds) required by the upper slide to cover a distance of 6.5 cm was noted. A shorter interval shows better Spreadability. Spreadability (S) was calculated as follows

$$S = M.L/t$$

Where,

S = Spreadability

M = weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide)

L = Length moved by glass slide

T = Time (sec) taken to separate the upper slide from the ground slide

The observations were tabulated in Table. No. 2

5. Calibration Curve^[13]

Kojic acid dipalmitate in methanol at 273 nm

Kojic acid Dipalmitate has absorbance in the UV range 273 nm when dissolved in an appropriate solvent (methanol). The calibration curve is plotted using standard solutions, and the absorbance is measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Procedure

100mg of the Kojic acid Dipalmitate was accurately weighed and dissolved in methanol: water in a 100ml standard volumetric flask. The volume was made up to 100ml and from the stock solution, solutions containing 2,4,6,8,10 µg/mL were prepared. The Absorbances of solution was determined spectrophotometrically at 273 nm.

The values are tabulated in Table No.3 and represented graphically by plotting Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) vs Absorbance in Graph 1

Niacinamide in methanol and distilled water (50:50) at 262 nm

Niacinamide has absorbance in the UV range 262 nm when dissolved in an appropriate solvent (methanol: water). The calibration curve is plotted using standard solutions, and the absorbance is measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Procedure

100mg of the Niacinamide was accurately weighed and dissolved in methanol: water in a 100ml standard volumetric flask. The volume was made up to 100ml and from the stock solution, solutions containing 2,4,6,8,10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were prepared. The Absorbances of solution was determined spectrophotometrically at 262 nm.

The values are tabulated in Table No.4 and represented graphically by plotting Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) vs Absorbance in Graph 2.

6. Drug content^[14,15,16]

Kojic acid dipalmitate drug content

Accurately weighed 1 g of emulgel formulation containing Kojic Acid Dipalmitate and transferred it to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Approximately 50 mL of methanol was added, and the mixture was sonicated for 20–30 minutes to extract the drug thoroughly from the emulgel base. The solution was then diluted up to 100 mL with methanol. The resulting solution was filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 1 to separate the insoluble excipients. From the filtrate, 1 mL was pipetted and diluted to 10 mL with methanol to obtain a suitable concentration within the calibration range (2–10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The absorbance of the sample solution was measured at 273 nm using methanol as a blank with a UV–Visible spectrophotometer. The drug content was determined using the calibration curve of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate. The values were tabulated in Table No. 5.

Niacinamide drug content

For the calculation of percentage drug content, 1 g of the gel was taken into a 10 mL volumetric flask and methanol was added. The mixture was shaken well, and the volume was made up to 10 mL with methanol. The solution was kept undisturbed for 2 hours and then

passed through filter paper. The supernatant was used to measure the absorbance using a spectrophotometer at 262 nm. The values were tabulated in Table No. 6.

***In-vitro* Diffusion study of emulgel^[17,18,19,20]**

The Franz diffusion cell apparatus is used for the *in-vitro* diffusion study. In this study the cellulose membrane is used. The membrane was carefully attached to the dialysis cell's hollow glass tube, and then the glass tube is filled with 1 gm of emulsion gel. Magnetic beads were used to agitate the phosphate buffer 7.4 pH solution that had been added to the receptor chamber. At specific interval of time, 1 ml of the sample was taken in aliquots, and the volume make to 10 ml. after the proper dilutions, the solution content was checked by using UV visible spectroscopy at 273 nm for kojic acid dipalmitate. The Procedure was repeated with phosphate buffer in niacinamide at 262 nm. The values were tabulated in Table. No 7 and Table. No 8 and represented graphically by plotting concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) vs absorbance in graph 3 and graph 4.

In-Vitro Diffusion Profile of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in Phosphate buffer at 273 nm were tabulated in Table. No 9 and represented graphically by time vs cumulative % of drug release in graph 5.

In-Vitro Diffusion Profile of Niacinamide in Phosphate buffer at 262 nm were tabulated in Table. No 10 and represented graphically by time vs cumulative % of drug release in graph 6.

RESULTS

Table No. 2: Evaluation Parameters for Kojic Acid Dipalmitate and Niacinamide Emulgel.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS	FORMULATION CODE			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
State	Semi solid	Semi solid	Semi solid	Semi solid
Colour	Milk white	Milk white	White	Pale white
Odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour	Pleasant odour
pH	5.5	5.8	6.0	6.4
Viscosity(cps)	732	749	832	856
Spreadability	Excellent	Good	Average	Average

Table No. 3: Standard Calibration Curve of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in methanol at 273 nm.

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance
1	2	0.145
2	4	0.289
3	6	0.435
4	8	0.578
5	10	0.721

Graph 1: Standard Calibration Curve of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in methanol at 273 nm.

Table No. 4: Standard Calibration Curve of Niacinamide in methanol : water at 262 nm.

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance
1	2	0.062
2	4	0.124
3	6	0.187
4	8	0.249
5	10	0.312

Graph 2: Standard Calibration Curve of Niacinamide in methanol: water at 262 nm.

Table No. 5: Drug content of kojic acid dipalmitate.

Formulation	% Drug Content
F1	99.24
F2	95.92
F3	89.86
F4	85.96

Table No. 6: Drug content of niacinamide.

Formulation	% Drug Content
F1	99.24
F2	95.92
F3	89.86
F4	85.96

Table No. 7: Standard Calibration Curve of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in Phosphate Buffer at 273 nm.

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance
1	2	0.155
2	4	0.300
3	6	0.450
4	8	0.590
5	10	0.740

Graph 3: Standard Calibration Curve of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in Phosphate Buffer at 273 nm.

Table No. 8: Standard Calibration Curve of Niacinamide in Phosphate Buffer at 262 nm.

S.no	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance
1	2	0.089
2	4	0.170
3	6	0.250
4	8	0.330
5	10	0.410

Graph 4: Standard Calibration Curve of Niacinamide in Phosphate Buffer at 262 nm.

Table No. 9: *In-Vitro* Diffusion Profile of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in Phosphate buffer at 273 nm.

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4
15	56	59	47	41
30	81	73	77	69
45	90	82	87	76
60	99.46	92.91	98.80	96.39

Graph 5: *In-Vitro* Diffusion Profile of Kojic Acid Dipalmitate in Phosphate buffer at 273 nm.

Table No. 10: *In-Vitro* Diffusion Profile of Niacinamide in Phosphate buffer at 262 nm.

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4
15	50	43	40	38
30	75	65	71	76
45	89	79	85	87
60	99.98	88.09	92.99	94.76

Graph 6: *In-Vitro* Diffusion Profile of Niacinamide in Phosphate buffer at 262 nm.

DISCUSSION

The current research work was conducted on the formulation and evaluation of an emulgel formulation of Kojic acid Dipalmitate and niacinamide. Emulgel formulation was selected as the dosage form because it provides the benefits of both emulsion and gel formulation, such as improved Spreadability, non-greasy texture, and improved patient compliance. The formulation showed an acceptable pH value for topical application and homogeneity without any phase separation.

The prepared formulations were tested for their organoleptic characteristics, and it was observed that there is no change in the organoleptic characteristics of the formulations. The Spreadability tests revealed that all the formulations possess good Spreadability. The viscosities of all the formulations were found to be in between 500-1000 cps, which shows that the formulations can be easily spreadable with less amount of shear. The pH values of the formulated emulgel were found to be in between 5.5-6.5, which shows that the formulation is safe for skin. The drug content of all the formulations were found to be within acceptable limits 90-100 % which indicates better uniformity and distribution of active ingredients.

From that, among all the formulation F1 showed a better spreadability, improved viscosity, acceptable pH and has a higher drug content and uniformity.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In the current investigation, the aim was the formulation and assessment of an emulgel formulation of Kojic acid Dipalmitate and niacinamide. The active components were chosen based on their skin-lightening, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. The emulgel formulation was selected to provide the benefits of both emulsions and gels. From this investigation, it can be concluded that the formulation of kojic acid and niacinamide emulgel possesses excellent properties of an emulgel and was found to be non-toxic, having acceptable pH, good homogeneity, and satisfactory physical characteristics, making it suitable for topical application. Among all the formulations, F1 having Carbopol 934 was found to have excellent organoleptic properties, acceptable pH, improved Spreadability, viscosity, good drug release and non-irritating properties.

It was concluded that a stable and effective formulation of emulgel of Kojic acid Dipalmitate and niacinamide was successfully developed. The formulation F1 was found to have good Spreadability, uniform drug content, and acceptable stability. Thus, the formulation F1 may

be selected for further *in vivo* studies if the results are found to be beneficial. Hence, the developed emulgel formulation can be considered as a promising topical formulation for the treatment of hyperpigmentation and cosmetic dermatology.

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